

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Los Angeles
Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia

IMPLEMENTING AN ONLINE PRECEPTORSHIP TRAINING MODULE FOR CRNAS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to improve the certified registered nurse anesthetist preceptor's comfort, confidence, satisfaction, and knowledge while precepting the student registered nurse anesthetist in the clinical setting. The project was adapted from a previous pilot study by Butler et al., 2022. The online education module was modified and deployed to 33 certified registered nurse anesthetists at Kaiser Permanente Panorama City Medical Center. Pre- and post-module data were collected before and after completion of the online education. The data showed no significant changes in the preceptor's comfort, confidence, satisfaction, and knowledge. A Spearman rank order correlative test revealed a negative correlation between the number of years of experience as a certified registered nurse anesthetist and their level of confidence with precepting a student registered nurse anesthetist from a differing ethnic background, which implicates the need for additional cultural and ethnic training. Future recommendations include the addition of audio narration to the educational module, exploring a hybrid model of preceptor education, and deploying the educational module to other facilities where certified registered nurse anesthetists precept student registered nurse anesthetists. Given the limited existing research on preceptor education, exploring strategies to enhance and support the role of certified registered nurse anesthetist preceptors in the clinical setting is vital.

Keywords: clinical education, CRNA preceptor education, education module, and precepting SRNAs.

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Background

The American Association of Nurse Anesthesiology (AANA, 2022) estimates that certified registered nurse anesthetists (CRNAs) perform 50 million anesthetics in urban and rural communities each year. Just as millions of patients put their trust in CRNAs to provide safe anesthesia, practicing student registered nurse anesthetists (SRNAs) trust that their clinical experiences would adequately prepare them to be safe and independent practitioners upon completing the program. At a minimum, SRNAs are required to complete at least 2000 clinical hours managing distinct and complex surgical cases, performing various practical skills, and caring for diverse patient populations (Council on Accreditation of Nurse Anesthesia Educational Programs [COA], 2022). At clinical sites, CRNAs primarily serve as preceptors, where they have a significant impact on preparing the SRNA's transition into practice.

CRNA preceptors are vital to the growth of SRNAs due to their clinical expertise and knowledge. A preceptor is recognized as an experienced clinician who serves as a teacher, facilitator, and role model to the student learner in the clinical setting (Omansky, 2010). Preceptorship effectively transforms didactic knowledge in the clinical environment by advancing skills and applied knowledge (Quek & Shorey, 2018). Preceptorship provides the ability for one-on-one learning experiences for SRNAs to fine-tune their skills while delivering anesthesia in and out of the operating room. As preceptors, CRNAs uphold their professional responsibility to provide clinical guidance, evaluate performance, and approve a patient-specific plan of care (COA, 2022). Each preceptor is expected to provide instructions that are "conducive to student learning" while also providing safe anesthesia care (COA, 2022, p. 23).

Although CRNAs are experts in their clinical knowledge and skill, many have not been equipped with the tools to facilitate adult learning (Elisha, 2008). Each preceptor has their style

of teaching, which might not correspond with the learning style of the SRNA (Scott-Herring & Singh, 2017a). One study found that CRNAs have differing perceptions of the characteristics of an effective clinical preceptor, indicating a lack of a standardized preceptor role (Smith et al., 2011). In addition, preceptors reported stress, dissatisfaction, and a lack of comfort with teaching (Scott-Herring & Singh, 2017a, 2017b). A well-developed CRNA preceptor training program could ameliorate many of these reported issues to improve the precepting experience.

Findings in the literature have supported the use of preceptor workshops to enhance the preceptor role of the CRNA (Easton et al., 2017; Elisha, 2008; Scott-Herring & Singh, 2017a, 2017b). However, a standardized guideline for a preceptor program does not exist, and formal preceptor education for CRNAs is optional in facilities with SRNAs. By contrast, other nursing professions, such as nurse practitioners and nurse educators, possess educational programs for preceptorship that demonstrate promising outcomes (Perryman, 2022; Ryan et al., 2017; Wu et al., 2018). These programs enhance the preceptor experience by strengthening knowledge and skills, teaching efficacy, and role preparedness, illustrating important implications for a standardized CRNA preceptor program. Despite this, there is minimal literature regarding the preceptorship education of CRNAs (Easton et al., 2017; Elisha, 2008; Scott-Herring & Singh, 2017a, 2017b). Among the limited research, Scott-Herring and Singh (2017a, 2017b) developed a CRNA preceptor workshop that illustrated positive outcomes that enhanced teaching techniques. The lack of an educational program is a missed opportunity to improve the effectiveness of preceptor satisfaction and preceptee educational outcomes.

Purpose Statement

This evidence-based project aimed to implement an online, interactive training module in a southern California hospital to prepare CRNAs to be effective preceptors. Specific aims for this

project included: a) implementing a revised CRNA preceptorship educational module incorporating the latest evidence and lessons learned from a recent pilot study, b) evaluating the effectiveness of the educational module, and c) making recommendations based on findings for future CRNA preceptor education development.

Preceptorship in the CRNA profession is vital to student growth and learning throughout the clinical experience. However, the precepting role can be arduous with the various teaching and learning styles associated with adult learning. The literature has demonstrated the benefits of a preceptorship program, such as personalized teaching methods and role preparedness. This project aimed to reduce some stressors experienced by CRNA preceptors by providing applied knowledge in the form of an educational module.

Review of Literature

The purpose of this project was to implement an online, interactive training module in a southern California hospital to prepare CRNAs to be effective preceptors. A literature review was conducted to gather pertinent information regarding preceptor training in the nurse anesthesia profession. Four electronic databases, PubMed, CINAHL Complete, Ovid, and Scopus, were used to search for current peer-reviewed literature published between 2017-2022. The California State University Fullerton (CSUF) School of Nursing librarian aided in the literature search to fully exhaust pertinent studies. The key terms included in the search were “CRNA,” “certified registered nurse anesthetist,” “nurse anesthetist,” “preceptor,” “mentor,” “preceptorship,” “mentorship,” “clinical education,” and “preceptor program.” The search excluded non-English publications and non-medical-related studies. Due to the limited results, the search was expanded to include articles published as early as 2000 and terms encompassing nurses and advanced practice registered nurses (APRNs), such as nurse practitioners (NPs) and midwives. Adjusted search terms included: “nurse,” “advanced practice nurses,” “nurse practitioners,” or “clinical nurse specialist.” The literature search revealed 444 results, of which eight studies were relevant, including two quasi-experimental studies, one mixed-methods cross-sectional study, four descriptive non-experimental studies, and one systematic review. In addition, three quality improvement (QI) projects were also included.

Benefits of Preceptor Training

Whether through online or traditional in-person workshops, training programs have been shown to prepare nurses for the preceptor role (Elisha, 2008; Liao et al., 2019; Rodrigues et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2022). Preceptors are responsible for providing patient care while concurrently educating a newer practitioner (Rodrigues et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2018).

These dual roles can result in stress and an impaired transfer of knowledge with underprepared preceptors (Amirehsani et al., 2019; Liao et al., 2019; Rodrigues et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2018). Various studies demonstrated that well-educated preceptors perform with greater self-efficacy when carrying out their role as an educator (Amirehsani et al., 2019; Liao et al., 2019; McNeil & Konicki, 2021; Rodrigues et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2022). Liao et al. (2019) implemented a clinical reasoning training workshop (CRTW), which consisted of seven hours of training and one hour of a small group discussion. Preceptors showed a statistically significant increase in clinical reasoning ($p < .001$) and self-efficacy ($p < .001$) after CRTW. These results illustrated that preceptors who participated in CRTW improved their assessment of students' learning needs, fostered student knowledge and skills with patient care, guided critical thinking and problem-solving skills, and provided timely feedback to enhance learning (Liao et al., 2019).

A descriptive qualitative design by Rodrigues et al. (2021) explored the perceptions of a web-based clinical pedagogy (WCP) program among nurse preceptors and found similar results as Liao et al. (2019). After participating in the WCP program, participants reported increased self-awareness, self-development, and confidence in precepting students (Rodrigues et al., 2021). Furthermore, the WCP program helped nurse preceptors adjust their teaching methods by adapting to the needs of the student learner, employing a methodological approach to teaching, and realizing their role as a facilitator of learning (Rodrigues et al., 2021).

Elisha's (2008) exploratory study further demonstrated that formal CRNA preceptorship training could instill knowledge of effective precepting practices while promoting long-term retention of these methods. Results from Elisha (2008) demonstrated an improvement in the preceptors' perceived behaviors and clinical preceptor knowledge following the training program. Preceptor training can be tailored to refresh the general knowledge of preceptors and

enhance reteaching skills with the support of their personal experiences (Elisha, 2008; McNeil & Konicki, 2021; Rodrigues et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2018). This training offers preceptors several teaching techniques to address diverse learning styles, skills to refine communication and clinical evaluation, and a deeper understanding of the roles and responsibilities of preceptors and students (McNeil & Konicki, 2021; Rodrigues et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2018).

Thus, trained and supported preceptors can promote a more valuable and memorable clinical experience for students (Burt et al., 2021). Preceptor training also results in increased satisfaction in their role as preceptors (Amirehsani et al., 2019; McNeil & Konicki, 2021). A standardized preceptor program allows preceptors to employ effective and individualized teaching plans depending on the student's learning styles and skill levels.

Effects on Student Outcomes

Due to the incongruence in expectations and training styles, preceptors and students can experience stressful educational encounters (Amirehsani et al., 2019; Elisha, 2008; McNeil & Konicki, 2021; Rodrigues et al., 2021). Additionally, students received fewer instances of verbal and ongoing constructive feedback than what was perceived by preceptors (Elisha, 2008). Furthermore, unstructured teaching strategies, such as reflection, observation, and "teach as taught," were the top teaching approaches utilized by preceptors, which were not shown to be effective in students' learning outcomes (McNeil & Konicki, 2021, p. 109). Lastly, preceptors acknowledged a need for standardized methods to personalize clinical teaching to the unique student learning styles (Burt et al., 2021). The disconnect between preceptor and preceptee expectations creates challenges in establishing an optimal learning experience. These inconsistencies in the preceptor-preceptee relationship restrict the effectiveness of bridging the knowledge-practice gap of students (McNeil & Konicki, 2021).

With the implementation of preceptor training, preceptors were more prepared to support clinical learning with students. Students were exposed to better teaching practices and conducive learning environments with trained preceptors (Liao et al., 2019). Additionally, students experienced personalized learning encounters, improved autonomy, and received regular performance feedback from preceptors who underwent training (Liao et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2018). Students were also more confident conducting skills and assessments when learning under a more standardized teaching method (Rodrigues et al., 2021). Hence, standardized preceptor training will enhance the training and outcomes of future practitioners.

Barriers to Preceptor Development

Although many studies support the implementation of preceptor education for its beneficial outcomes, barriers exist that prevent the ease of training implementation. In a cross-sectional descriptive survey design by McNeil and Konicki (2021), NPs reported that the top barriers to preceptor development were lack of preceptor training (63%, n = 123), time (56.9%, n = 111), and perceived costs (18.9%, n = 37). Additionally, a systematic review by Wu et al. (2018) found access to learning experiences and time constraints as barriers to attending workshops. Reduced accessibility encompasses the inability to undertake preceptor training due to a lack of available workshops or challenges attending workshops due to limited dates and times. Along with time and accessibility, Burt et al. (2021) found that lack of compensation to participate in training was another barrier. When asked about the motivations to precept, Amirehsani et al. (2019) and Burt et al. (2021) found participants to be incentivized if compensation, such as continuing education credits or financial compensation, was available.

Barriers need to be addressed to improve the precepting experience. Implementing and executing a formal preceptor training program requires institutional support and resources, such

as written information on student objectives, goals, and the adult learning style, as well as communication with faculty, which would make preceptor training an effortless option for CRNAs (Amirehsani et al., 2019; McNeil & Konicki, 2021). A proposed solution to address the issue of accessibility is through an online preceptor educational format

Traditional Versus Online Education Methods

Both web-based and in-person preceptor education illustrate promising outcomes in the preceptor experience. Liao et al. (2019) concluded that preceptor knowledge and self-efficacy were enhanced, resulting in better mentorship. Similarly, in a descriptive study by Elisha (2008), in-person education for CRNA preceptors resulted in positive outcomes where participants preferred an active learning style, such as class discussions and role-playing, over a traditional lecture format (p. 290).

In contrast to the traditional delivery methods of preceptor education, web-based programs also offer favorable results. A qualitative study by Rodrigues et al. (2021) found that participants felt their WCP program improved confidence, increased self-awareness, and aided in adapting to individual student needs. Additionally, a systematic review by Wu et al. (2018) demonstrated that online learning modules increased knowledge, self-confidence, and leadership practices. Preceptors also reported high levels of satisfaction with online training due to its ease of access and reliability (Wu et al., 2018). A prospective quasi-experimental study by Wu et al. (2022) compared the effectiveness of a WCP program with an in-person preceptorship course among nurse preceptors at a tertiary hospital in Singapore. When contrasting the efficacy of a web-based preceptor program with face-to-face instruction, Wu et al. (2022) found similar outcomes in clinical teaching competencies and self-efficacy among the preceptors. The self-efficacy assessment initially showed higher scores for those who attended the face-to-face

instruction; yet, at the 6-month follow-up, there were no differences between the WCP and control group (Wu et al., 2022). Thus, Wu et al. (2022) demonstrated that a web-based program is as efficacious as face-to-face instruction.

Web-based preceptor training offers flexibility and produces similar education outcome efficacy, enabling nurses to review material after taking the course and master the program's training goals (Wu et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2022). Online education can potentially encourage participation in clinical preceptor education due to its flexibility, ease of access, and convenience (Rodrigues et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2022). Furthermore, web-based programs can be standardized to provide consistent and up-to-date content (Rodrigues et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2022).

Despite the promising outcomes associated with online learning, obstacles remain that need to be addressed. Technological difficulties can present challenges in delivering web-based preceptor educational material (Rodrigues et al., 2021). Additionally, online learning inherently cannot duplicate in-person learning. Techniques such as active group discussion are crucial to adult learning but cannot be recreated in self-paced online training (Elisha, 2008). Online training offers many benefits for professional development but limits the dynamics present in face-to-face instructions. A hybrid approach to delivering preceptor educational training is a potential method to provide flexibility and enhanced engagement (Wu et al., 2018).

Findings from Quality Improvement Projects

Research regarding preceptorship education for CRNAs is limited; however, valuable lessons can be learned from completed QI projects that focused on providing preceptor education to CRNAs. In a QI project by Scott-Herring and Singh (2017a), a formalized CRNA preceptor training program was implemented that aimed to improve overall comfort, confidence, and

satisfaction in clinical precepting. An increase was observed in total scores for satisfaction ($p = 0.002$) and comfort ($p = 0.009$) (Scott-Herring & Singh, 2017a). However, confidence ($p = 0.102$) did not illustrate a statistical difference in pre and post-program completion; this result may have been attributed to the prior preceptor education and small sample size (Scott-Herring & Singh, 2017a). In a subsequent QI project by Scott-Herring and Singh (2017b), completion of the CRNA workshop resulted in significant increases in scores across satisfaction, comfort, and confidence ($p < 0.001$). Notably, these participants (82%) never received formal preceptor training or education (Scott-Herring & Singh, 2017b).

Another QI work by Easton et al. (2017) focused on developing and evaluating a CRNA Preceptor Training Tutorial (CPiTT) to improve the precepting experience. The CPiTT was modified to include debriefing skills and tools, education timeouts before each case, and proper communication of concerns or issues. Moreover, a preceptorship survey was distributed to establish a baseline of precepting behaviors and found that CRNAs may not be aware of the teaching techniques they use, demonstrating a need for education on pedagogical approaches. Furthermore, Easton et al. (2017) identified that only 62% of participants believed that formal preceptor training would be necessary. The authors plan to fully implement the CPiTT across other medical facilities and nurse anesthesia programs to improve the preceptor experience.

In conclusion, these recent QI works illustrate the promising outcomes of a CRNA preceptor training program. As demonstrated by Scott Herring and Singh's (2017b) project, the implementation of a CRNA preceptor workshop produced positive outcomes, increasing preceptor satisfaction, comfort, and confidence. Furthermore, these works highlight the lack of prior preceptor education among many CRNAs, thus establishing the need for a preceptor training program (Easton et al., 2017; Scott Herring & Singh, 2017b). Therefore, minimal

literature on CRNA preceptor education raises the need for an evidence-based CRNA preceptorship training program.

Consensus for Preceptor Education

Despite the benefits of preceptor training, many preceptors reported never participating in any preceptor training or educational course (Elisha, 2008; McNeil & Konicki, 2021; Scott-Herring & Singh, 2017b). This missing intervention is apparent as studies revealed that participants would want formal preceptor training or resources (Amirehsani et al., 2019; Burt et al., 2021). Additionally, preceptors reported the need for standardized preceptor education to facilitate the delivery of safe, quality patient care (Burt et al., 2021; McNeil & Konicki, 2021; Scott-Herring & Singh, 2017a, 2017b). Similarly, most advanced practice nurses and physicians from Burt et al. (2021) discussed that they feel prepared as preceptors. This discrepancy may be due to differing levels of experience and success as a preceptor. Some argue that preceptor education can add value to the consistency and delivery of teaching (Elisha, 2008; Rodrigues et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2022)

Most studies agree that continuing education for preceptors can positively affect preceptor teaching and student learning outcomes (Elisha, 2008; Rodrigues et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2022). Unfortunately, many of the studies lack generalizability due to small sample sizes. Additionally, no standardized educational content was used across the studies. Furthermore, there were inconsistencies in the measurable outcomes of the effectiveness of the preceptor training. The variety between studies and lack of research extrapolates that stakeholders do not find trained preceptors a priority. In spite of that, the desire for an educational program exists but cannot be executed correctly without overcoming barriers.

In summary, this literature review revealed that formal preceptor education could have lasting positive impacts on the CRNA and APRN profession. These benefits include the development of efficacious preceptors, improved precepting experiences, and enhanced transferability of knowledge. Although the studies differed in their delivery of the preceptor educational training, web-based or in-person preceptor education is advantageous for CRNA clinical preceptors to mitigate the knowledge-practice gap. Thus, the utilization of preceptorship education should be standardized to ensure CRNAs have improved confidence, comfort, knowledge, and satisfaction as preceptors.

Supporting Framework

Evidence-based practice (EBP) synthesizes the best available research evidence to address a clinical problem promoting safe, quality, and cost-effective health care for patients (Grove & Gray, 2019). The Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice, developed initially in 1994, is a widely used framework that supports the integration of EBP in the clinical arena through a systematic multi-step approach (Titler et al., 2001). It was crucial to have a framework, such as the Iowa Model, to guide the translation of EBP into the clinical forum. A supporting framework allows clinicians to follow a pragmatic roadmap to assist in making decisions from a clinical and systems standpoint (Bonnell & Smith, 2021). The Iowa Model consists of seven distinct steps and was recently revised in 2017 (Figure A1) to incorporate a streamlined and user-friendly approach (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). As such, the Iowa Model has been widely applied by many facilities to successfully integrate new evidence into practice. For instance, Robbins et al. (2017) successfully utilized the Iowa Model to implement a preceptor training program to help train burn nurses. Similarly, Kuensting et al. (2020) relied on the Iowa Model to develop web-based training modules for nurse practitioner (NP) preceptors to guide students through their clinical training. Because of its user-friendly process flow that has been demonstrated to effectively drive evidence-based practice changes, the Iowa Model was selected for this DNP project (Figure A2) to guide the implementation of a CRNA preceptor training program at a Southern California Kaiser Permanente (KP) facility.

Identifying Triggering Issues and Opportunities

A triggering issue was identified in the Iowa Model's first step. The practice issue of concern in this DNP project was the lack of a formal and standardized CRNA preceptor program. The lack of standardized preceptor training leads to rigid teaching styles that may not benefit all

types of learners (Burt et al., 2021; McNeil & Konicki, 2021). Despite this, a limited number of facilities utilize a CRNA preceptor program, albeit its capability to enhance knowledge transfer and furnish a superior precepting experience (Elisha, 2008; McNeil & Konicki, 2021).

State the Question or Purpose

The second step of the Iowa Model was to state the question or purpose. For this DNP project, a formalized CRNA preceptor education module was implemented to evaluate its effects on preceptor confidence, comfort, knowledge, and satisfaction. Based on lessons learned from a recent pilot study by Butler et al. (2022), modifications were made to improve a developed educational module. Afterward, this module was implemented and evaluated with CRNAs at a Southern California KP facility, where data was further analyzed to optimize and inform the content and delivery of the educational module.

First Decision Point

Subsequently, the first decision point in the Iowa Model was reached, determining whether the identified issue was significant or a priority to the organization (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). Prior literature supported the needs and benefits of a preceptorship program. Since KP of Southern California does not currently have a preceptor training program for CRNAs, the organization identified a CRNA preceptorship program as a priority.

Form a Team

As highlighted by the Iowa Model in the third step, forming a team was necessary to plan, conduct, and evaluate the project (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). The team for this DNP project consisted of three DNP student nurse anesthetists from Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia (KPSA), one KPSA faculty advisor, and one California State University, Fullerton (CSUF) faculty advisor. Additional interdisciplinary members were also included to support the

delivery of change, such as statisticians, technological advisors, and clinical nurse educators at the site.

Assemble, Appraise, and Synthesize the Body of Evidence

The Iowa Model Collaborative's (2017) fourth step involved performing a literature review to find the highest level of evidence and synthesize findings and conclusions. A literature review was conducted regarding preceptor education for CRNAs, advanced practice nurses, and graduate-level nurses. As mentioned in the literature review, there are minimal studies regarding CRNA preceptor education. However, there is evidence that supported the positive benefits of preceptor education for registered nurses (RNs) and other advanced practice registered nurses (APRNs), such as improved self-efficacy and satisfaction as a preceptor (Liao et al., 2019; McNeil & Konicki, 2021). Additional studies identified a need for formalized education to ensure preceptors are adequately equipped to educate incoming students (Burt et al., 2021; McNeil & Konicki, 2021). Though some preceptors felt prepared to undertake the teaching role, most desired formal training to understand adult learning styles and become better educators (Amirehsani et al., 2019; Burt et al., 2021).

Second Decision Point

At this point in the model, the second decision point assessed whether or not there is enough evidence to support a practice change (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). During the literature search, there was limited literature involving the standardization of CRNA preceptor education. However, the literature review elucidated the beneficial outcomes of preceptor training that are evidenced across the nursing profession. Therefore, sufficient evidence supported the development and implementation of CRNA preceptor education.

Design and Pilot the Practice Change

This fifth step involved the engagement of patients and families, identification of resources and approval, creation of an evaluation and implementation plan, collection of data throughout the pilot change, and promotion of the adoption of the change (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). A clinical teaching module was previously developed to enhance preceptor knowledge, satisfaction, confidence, and comfort (Butler et al., 2022). This DNP project evaluated the data retrieved from an initial pilot study by Butler et al. (2022); the module was deployed to all CRNA clinical coordinators of Southern California Kaiser Permanente. Subsequently, the module was modified and enhanced based on results and expert feedback. The module was further revised and then implemented on a larger scale encompassing CRNA preceptors at a single Southern California Kaiser Permanente facility.

Third Decision Point

At this point in the process flow outlined in the Iowa Model, it was necessary to identify whether the proposed change was appropriate for adoption (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). During the implementation phase, CRNA preceptors at a single Southern California KP facility were provided with a pre- and post-intervention questionnaire to determine the effectiveness of the CRNA preceptor module. The module was evaluated based on responses to the questionnaires, which included its accessibility and ease of use. The technological aspects of the module were designed to be easy to navigate and easily accessible by CRNA preceptors. Furthermore, if the results of the educational module were deemed to improve preceptor confidence, comfort, satisfaction, and knowledge, the module would be further refined to prepare its deployment to all KP facilities in Southern California.

Integrate and Sustain the Practice Change

The sixth step of the Iowa Model includes identifying key personnel responsible for integrating and sustaining practice change. Key personnel are essential in solidifying the proposed change and monitoring and reporting key outcomes: preceptor confidence, comfort, satisfaction, and knowledge. Garnering support from key stakeholders, such as the CRNAs at the KP facility, is essential to sustaining the outcomes of the educational module by demonstrating its value to the CRNAs' professional practice. Thus, the CRNA staff were presented with findings from the literature review to demonstrate the practice gap and the potential beneficial outcomes of the preceptor educational module. With the garnered interest, a selected individual assisted the team in spearheading this project's implementation.

Champions are essential individuals who provide peer influence that help implement and sustain practice changes (Cullen et al., 2018). The clinical coordinator assumed the role of a practice change champion. The clinical coordinator was an ideal candidate for the role of the champion as he or she was a leader who linked the staff CRNAs with SRNAs. Selecting a practice change champion showed leadership support for change.

To remind stakeholders of the goals and outcomes of the project, reinfusion of the educational module will occur as needed. As Cullen et al. (2018) and Iowa Model Collaborative (2017) emphasized, continuous monitoring of process and outcome measures is necessary to plan for reinfusion. Constant communication with the stakeholders regarding this project's status, such as through monthly meetings, help keep the stakeholders focused and prevent regression of the practice change (Cullen et al., 2018).

For sustainability, the preceptorship module can be deployed for new-hire CRNAs and offered as a refresher course for established CRNAs. It can be evaluated yearly for its efficacy in

improving and maintaining comfort, confidence, satisfaction, and knowledge with precepting SRNAs. After each evaluation, the learning content can be revised based on the results received from the pre-and post-module surveys to identify areas of improvement and accommodate current educational demands. This preceptor module can also be implemented and evaluated for future projects at other southern CA KP anesthesia departments.

Disseminate Results

The last step of the Iowa Model required the internal and external dissemination of results to share lessons learned and promote the future formation of evidenced-based practice (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). Internal dissemination allowed facilities within an organization to understand how results from an implemented practice change encompassed evidence-based practice and mobilized interest for prospective integration into other facilities (Cullen et al., 2018). External dissemination promoted the expansion of nursing knowledge and emboldened the adoption of evidence-based practice changes in other organizations (Cullen et al., 2018).

This DNP project was scheduled to disseminate results in December 2023 at the California State University Consortium (CSUC) and Kaiser Permanente (KP) Dissemination Day. The project results were presented to peers, CSUC team leaders, and KP School of Anesthesia team leaders. Additionally, the results were presented to Kaiser Permanente Panorama City Medical Center (KPPCMC) during a scheduled team meeting to inform stakeholders. Finally, a manuscript was sent to a peer-reviewed journal of choice.

By disseminating the results of this project internally and externally, it was anticipated that additional improvements to the educational module would be made, which would then be deployed on a larger scale to other KP facilities. Furthermore, it was believed that the lessons learned from this project would promulgate the adoption of this educational module by other

organizations in order to align with the Council of Accreditation's (COA) recommendation that all anesthesia providers provide safe and adequate clinical instruction (COA, 2022).

Additionally, the results of this project may highlight the need for professional preceptor training that begins at the graduate level.

The Iowa Model has historically shown success for quality improvement projects in nursing practice. With guidance from the Iowa Model, this project team executed its steps to increase the project's success for implementation and maintenance. With proper implementation, the project team evaluated the educational module's effectiveness and sought changes to be made for future preceptor education.

Methods

The development and implementation of an online CRNA preceptor education stemmed from the lack of an existing training program at a southern California Kaiser Permanente (KP) facility. Although there was minimal evidence regarding CRNA preceptorship, specifically, a literature review of preceptor programs among other advanced practice nursing disciplines illustrated positive outcomes for improving the preceptor experience by increasing role preparedness, bolstering comfort in teaching, and strengthening knowledge. Given the noted benefits demonstrated in other advanced practice nursing roles during preceptorship education found in literature, the project aimed to implement an online CRNA preceptor education module to improve preceptor knowledge, satisfaction, confidence, and comfort.

Design

The design of the project was a quality improvement project (QI). Quality improvement was a systematic approach that aimed to improve patient care by developing professional skills and clinical collaboration (Jones et al., 2018). The Iowa Model was used as a supporting framework to guide the project systematically (Appendix A). Utilizing the Iowa Model supported the integration of a CRNA preceptor educational module into clinical practice based on current evidence.

Ethical Considerations

A proposal was submitted to and approved by both Kaiser Permanente and California State University, Fullerton Institutional Review Boards (IRB) as shown in Figure B1 and Figure B2, Appendix B. Informed consent to participate in the project was obtained electronically when participants elected to participate in the online educational module. The informed consent document outlined the preceptorship module's benefits, including enhanced preceptor-preceptee

relationships, individualization of teaching, and professional development. Participants were also informed that participation had minimal to no risk to the user. Prospective participants were provided with the aims and procedures of the project. Additionally, participants were informed that participation was voluntary and could withdraw from the study at any time. Furthermore, participants were ensured that their responses remained anonymous by masking internet protocol (IP) addresses and excluding any personal identifying information (e.g., names and birthdates) from the results. Lastly, the project team members undertook the necessary steps to provide continuing education unit credits as compensation for completing the educational module. Participants were compensated with 1.5 hours of CEUs when requirements were met per AANA guidelines.

Sample and Setting

The project's sample included CRNAs employed at KPPCMC. The hospital was staffed with 25 full-time CRNAs and eight per diem CRNAs. KPPCMC CRNAs staffed ten operating rooms and managed patients in the labor and delivery unit. Inclusion criteria included board-certified registered nurse anesthetists who voluntarily participated in the online educational module. Exclusion criteria included those who did not have access to internet services. Participants were recruited through convenience sampling at the facility's monthly staff meeting.

Interventions

Online Educational Module Development

An online, interactive educational preceptor module was previously developed and deployed in a pilot project to improve preceptor knowledge, satisfaction, confidence, and comfort (Butler et al., 2022). The educational content of the module was based on a review of the literature and information garnered from content experts. Topics of the CRNA preceptor

education module covered the roles and responsibilities of the CRNA preceptor, types of adult learning styles, conflict management and resolution, and effective feedback skills. Adaptations to this first iteration of the preceptor educational module were based on lessons learned and data points gathered from the pilot project. Changes to the online module included modifications in the educational content, as well as a complete transition from Articulate Rise, the former creator platform, to Articulate Storyline. The current iteration of the module was trialed by four faculty members from KPSA and one faculty member from CSUF, utilizing varying electronic modes of delivery (e.g., desktop, laptop, tablet, and smartphone). Their expert feedback was incorporated into the module to improve ease of use, increase content clarity, and identify grammatical errors. An instructional design librarian from CSUF was also consulted to enhance the user experience by addressing the navigational and accessibility aspects of the educational module. Meetings were also conducted with KPSA's informational technology (IT) engineer to assist with the deployment of the module through KPSA's learning management system, Moodle.

Procedure

During a bi-monthly anesthesia department staff meeting, the team virtually presented the project via PowerPoint at KPPCCMC on Microsoft Teams. The presentation was an opportunity to garner participant interest in the project. CRNAs at KPPCCMC were sent an electronic (email) invitation to participate in the project, which also included a copy of the informed consent form and step-by-step instructions on how to access the online educational module. The link to the educational module was accessible on any mobile device or computer; however, users were advised to use their desktop or laptop for an enhanced user experience. The team's contact information was provided to participants for help regarding technical and access issues.

Before accessing the educational module, participants were informed of their voluntary participation in the project and directed to the demographic (Appendix D) and CRNA Preceptor Pre-module survey (Appendix E). After completing the surveys, participants gained access to the educational modules. Participants were given three weeks to complete the educational module, which took approximately 1.5 hours to complete. The online educational module was formatted so participants could complete it at their own pace; their progress was saved if they left at any point in the module. Participants received reminder emails to complete the module 14 days, 7 days, and 2 days before the module closed. Upon completion of the educational module, the participants were asked for their feedback via the CRNA Preceptor Post-module survey (Appendix F) and subsequently a final graded quiz.

Method of Evaluation

Outcome Measures

A pre (Appendix E) and post-module survey (Appendix F) were used to evaluate CRNA preceptor confidence, comfort, and satisfaction. The participant's confidence was the first outcome measure of the quality improvement project. Confidence could be defined as the self-perceived ability to perform tasks or deal with challenging situations (Walsh et al., 2021). Perry (2011) also described confidence as the "person's belief that he or she could succeed" (p. 219). Self-confidence could be complicated as it could be influenced by internal and external factors (Perry, 2011). Some internal factors Perry (2011) stated included self-esteem and emotional intelligence. Some external factors that could fluctuate a person's sense of self-confidence included the environment and situation (Perry, 2011). CRNA preceptors encountered many different SRNAs that contributed to changing the preceptor's situation with each encounter. With the institution of the preceptor education module, preceptors could learn to control different

situations confidently. This project measured the effect of the preceptor education module on confidence via pre- and post-survey scores.

Comfort was defined by the International Classification for Nursing Practice (ICNP) as a sense of bodily well-being or physical relief (International Council of Nurses, 2017). However, comfort was a complex and subjective term that encompassed more than physical qualities. It also included emotional and psychosocial realms, such as feelings of ease or alleviation of anxiety concerning stressful contexts (Pinto et al., 2017). Other descriptors of comfort included having a sense of control, satisfaction of needs, pleasant experiences, and the absence of discomfort (Pinto et al., 2017). The project measured comfort through pre- and post-survey scores on the feelings of CRNA preceptors to actively coach and teach SRNAs with varying learning styles.

Another outcome measure that was evaluated in the project was satisfaction. Satisfaction was defined as the "fulfillment of a want or need" (Merriam-Webster, n.d.). Accordingly, educational satisfaction was the fulfillment of academic experiences based on learning readiness, teacher-student interactions, course content, and learning immersion (Park & Kim, 2022). Frederick Herzberg's two-factor motivational theory (1959) identified factors that positively impacted satisfaction: achievement, growth, recognition, advancement, responsibility, and the work itself. In a QI project by Scott-Herring and Singh (2017b), the implementation of CRNA preceptor training education resulted in increased satisfaction, as illustrated by improved post-workshop survey scores. For the project, the pre- and post-survey scores of question one were evaluated to assess satisfaction with the educational preparation of SRNAs.

The outcome measure of preceptor knowledge was also evaluated. Knowledge was vital to nursing professional development (McEwen & Wills, 2019). Knowledge was the accurate

perception of reality through learning (McEwen & Wills, 2019, p. 27). The ICNP defined knowledge as “a content of thinking based upon acquired wisdom or learned information or skills, cognizance, and recognition of information” (International Council of Nurses, 2017, Code 10011042). In a study by Elisha (2008), CRNA preceptor knowledge was enhanced after participating in a CRNA educational curriculum. Thus, to assess preceptor knowledge in this project, the pre- and post-survey scores were compared.

Evaluation Tools

Participant demographic information, including gender, race, years of experience, and background, was collected using the CRNA Preceptor Demographics Survey (Appendix B). M. Scott-Herring, DNP, MS, CRNA (personal communication, October 26, 2022), created the surveys, and permission was granted to use them for this project. In Scott-Herring and Singh (2017a), the surveys were assessed for face and content validity through three CRNAs with more than 5 years of experience precepting SRNAs. Furthermore, Sandau et al. (2011) established internal reliability and calculated a Cronbach α coefficient of 0.82 for the preceptor surveys. The 5-point Likert scale presented in the pre- and post-workshop survey by Sandau et al. (2011) and Scott-Herring and Singh (2017b) will be modified where 1 is “strongly disagree”, 2 is “disagree,” 3 is “neither disagree nor agree,” 4 is “agree,” and 5 is “strongly agree” (Simms et al., 2019; Taherdoost, 2019). These modifications are based on lessons learned from the pilot study by Butler et al. (2022); in their study, the original response options for the Likert scale did not offer a clear delineation for positive and negative responses from participants. As a result of the changes to the response Likert scale, questions in the pre- and post- module survey were also altered from a question format to a statement format for clarity purposes. For example, question one of the pre- module survey was modified from “*How satisfied are you with your previous*

preparation regarding the education of SRNAs?” to “I am satisfied with my previous preparation regarding the education of SRNAs.”

The post-survey included Likert scale questions and open-ended questions that extracted the functionality and clarity of the online educational module. The following questions will be included: *“The educational module was easy to navigate”* and *“The content of the module was presented clearly and succinctly.”* The following open-ended questions will also be included to address the module’s technological aspects and content presentation: *“What recommendations do you have to improve the module?”* and *“If any technical issues occurred, please list them here.”* The feedback obtained from the participants was utilized to further enhance the training module for future implementation.

Data Collection and Analysis

The collected data was extracted and organized using Microsoft Excel and analyzed with IBM SPSS Statistics. The pre- and post-module survey assessed knowledge, satisfaction, comfort, and confidence outcome measures. The pre and post-module surveys consisted of questions scored using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The categorical measures were summarized using counts and percentages. Survey scores will be summarized using medians and means and then contrasted between the pre- and post-module surveys to analyze the outcome measures. The demographic surveys were analyzed using descriptive statistics resulting in frequencies and percentages. Three open-ended questions in the post-module survey were individually reviewed by the project team for common themes.

In essence, an online preceptorship module was obtained and modified based on lessons learned from a previous pilot project. By illustrating this project’s methodology, organization and structure was developed to impart the necessary steps for successful implementation.

Operationalization of these key variables assisted with measuring and evaluating the outcomes of this module. Hence, utilization of Dr. Mary Scott-Herring's validated pre- and postworkshop tools significantly aided in data gathering after implementation. Finally, the data was analyzed to evaluate the efficacy of the module in achieving its aims to produce greater knowledge, satisfaction, confidence, and comfort for a CRNA preceptors.

Results

Quantitative Analysis

The online educational module was deployed at KPPCMC for three weeks, from October 3, 2023, until October 24, 2023. Nine out of 33 CRNAs took the online educational module and completed the pre- and post-module survey, yielding a response rate of approximately 27%.

Each demographic variable had its frequency and corresponding percentage measured (Table G1). The sample consisted of primarily women (78%). Ages ranged from 30 to 63 years, with a mean age of 40. Approximately 78% of the participants were non-Hispanic. Of non-Hispanic participants the dominant ethnic background was White or Caucasian (67%). Within the sample pool, 67% were nurses for over 20 years, and 33% were previously SRNAs at KPPCMC. Forty-four percent of CRNAs graduated from a front-loaded program, 78% hold a master's degree, and 22% were pursuing a doctoral degree. While 22% of participants had one year or less of experience as a CRNA, 78% had five years or greater of experience. Most (78%) of the CRNAs have never participated in a CRNA preceptorship course; however, 56% have previously participated in a nurse preceptor course.

Regarding the pre- and post-module survey, the total scores were calculated, and the statistical means and medians were extracted. The medians for the pre- and post-module survey remained the same at 33. However, total mean scores slightly increased from 31.4 on the pre-module survey to 32 on the post-module survey. Significance was determined between the paired data by evaluating the median differences through the non-parametric Wilcoxon signed-rank test (Table G2). Significance was identified if $p < .05$. There were no significant differences between the pre- and post-module scores. Despite no significant differences, there was an increase in means from 3.5 to 4.2 for pre- and post-module statement one regarding satisfaction with

preceptorship education. Moreover, a Cronbach α coefficient was calculated at .90 and .88 for the pre- and post-module surveys, respectively, to ensure a high internal consistency.

Spearman's rank-order correlation was also used to determine any significant relationships between the data gathered from the demographic and pre- and post-module surveys (Table G3). Demographic data such as age, years as a CRNA, and number of years working as a CRNA at KPPCMC were included in the calculation. There were negative correlations found between pre- ($r = -.55, p = .125$) and post-module ($r = -.52, p = .152$) survey statement five, "I am confident with working with a SRNA of a different ethnic background than mine," and number of years working as a CRNA at KPPCMC. Another distinct finding was the weak correlation between age and ability to navigate the online module ($r = .06, p = .889$) and module content ($r = .08, p = .849$). Overall, no significant correlations were established between the survey scores and demographic data.

Qualitative Analysis

The post-module survey presented at the end of the module included two open-ended questions that inquired about the functionality and possible improvements participants suggested for the educational module. Responses are displayed in Table D4, Appendix D. Of nine participants, six participants did not have comments regarding technical issues during the lesson. Two of the nine participants had no feedback for further improvements to the module. The following analysis of the two open-ended questions below assessed the common themes of the responses.

Limited Time with Busy Schedules

Aside from working as a CRNA and having other life responsibilities, allocating time to complete the education module proved challenging for CRNAs. Of nine participants, two

requested the ability to personalize the playback speed of the slides. Both participants asked for the slides to have full control of the playback speed and control the advancement to subsequent slide. These statements represented the importance of user-controlled speed to the online learning experience. The ability to control speed could help learners understand the educational material at a pace that was appropriate for the learner. These comments also disclosed the limited time participants had for the module and would like the time spent on the module to be minimal. One participant stated that the module was "too long" (Table D4). These three comments echoed Burt et al. (2021) and McNeil and Konicki's (2021) statement of the limited time that APRNs experience and, thus, a barrier to obtaining preceptor education. Adult learning presented a unique challenge to the project's participants. It is essential to allow user-controlled learning to provide a practical learning experience for a busy adult learner.

Multimedia Online Learning vs. In-Person Learning

Two participants requested additional multimedia material for multimedia learning; one participant specifically suggested adding voice recording to the slide (Table D4). The current videos and interactive activities in the educational module were well received by the participants. There was a need for more multimedia learning to cater to different learning styles, such as auditory learning. The inclusivity of all learning styles should be a priority for enhancing learning material retention. Although most participants thought positively about an online educational module, one participant suggested that the material was best suited for an in-person learning experience. Overall, most of the participants did not discredit the learning experience of the preceptor education module.

Summary

Overall, there was a positive reaction to the online CRNA preceptor education module. Participants stated that the module was beneficial and that the module videos were “fun to watch” (Table D4). In addition, participants said that it should be a requirement to CRNA education. By addressing the clarity of a few survey questions, as suggested by one participant, the educational module can be an additional resource to CRNAs. Fortunately, participants did not encounter any significant technical issues. Moreover, there were no issues accessing Moodle or navigating through Articulate Storyline.

Discussion

Through a revised online preceptor educational module, this DNP study aimed to increase the CRNA preceptor's comfort, confidence, satisfaction, and knowledge by measuring pre- and post-module survey data. This study showed that most participants lacked prior training as CRNA preceptors, which is consistent with existing research on CRNA preceptor training programs. This data highlights the necessity for establishing a standardized preceptor training program among CRNAs. The increase in means from pre to post-module survey statement one indicated greater satisfaction with preceptor education after completing the online module. Moreover, the favorable response to the online module from the CRNAs at KPPCCMC represents a promising step toward developing and sustaining an effective preceptor education. As identified in the Iowa Model (2017), it is necessary to have stakeholder buy-in to integrate and sustain a practice. While no significant changes were observed in the measured outcomes of this study, this may be due to limitations discussed in the following sections.

Strengths and Implications

Provider Directed Online Study

Provider-directed independent study provided the participants flexibility to navigate their busy schedules. Participants could do the module independently and were not confined to completing it in one sitting. Not only was the completion of the module flexible, but the user also controlled the module material to allow enough time for participants to read. Users were able to access the module from any electronic device. In theory, CRNAs could have done the module on their personal devices when on break or lunch during work hours. Wu et al. (2022) discussed an insignificant difference between online and in-person learning. Due to its flexibility, convenience, and ease of use (Rodrigues et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2022), this study

demonstrates that an online learning modality can be easily incorporated in the future to advance and standardize the CRNA preceptor experience.

While online learning modalities proved to be a viable solution to delivering educational material, carefully constructing its technological and foundational elements was integral to its success. There were common perceptions of an inverse relationship between age and digital literacy; however, a heterogeneity of technological abilities was present among older adults depending on life circumstances, such as work experiences and digital exposure (McCosker et al., 2021). Our online module demonstrated minimal correlations between age and ability to navigate online content. Correspondingly, most participants perceived the online module and its respective content as “easy to navigate” on post-module survey questions eight and nine. The conducted meetings between an instructional design expert and the IT engineer helped facilitate an online module that accommodates the varying technological skills of our target demographic. Specific interventions included improving accessibility functions, placing navigational buttons in consistent locations, and ascertaining easy-to-read text. As our findings show, the meticulous consideration of how the educational content is presented plays a vital factor in successful implementation.

Complete Data Sets

One of the issues faced in the pilot study was a lack of complete data sets; some participants only completed a pre-module or a post-module survey. Based on this information, the pre- and post-module surveys were directly integrated into the educational module. Before accessing the educational module, participants must complete the demographic and pre-module survey. Once the module was completed in its entirety, users were directed to make their

responses for the post-module survey. This iteration of the preceptor education module delivered complete data sets and prevented the loss of participants within the sample size.

Limitations

Transition to Storyline Articulate

While creating the CRNA preceptor education module, switching from the previous platform, Articulate Rise, to Articulate Storyline proved challenging. Articulate Storyline was less user-friendly, lacking intuitive features. Informal self-training through online tutorials and browser searches was necessary to acquire a baseline working knowledge of the program. Furthermore, collaboration within the Storyline Articulate platform was burdensome; multiple users could not work on the project simultaneously. Thus, team members had to coordinate with one another to ensure that the most recent version of the module was edited. In consequence, the number of hours dedicated to learning the program and reinventing the study module limited the time the module was active for participants to complete.

Sample Size

Another limitation of the study was a small data set. The educational module was deployed to 33 CRNAs at KPPCMC. Only nine of the 33 CRNAs at KPPCMC participated in the study. A more extensive data set may have revealed significant correlations and themes (Grove & Gray, 2019). Despite incentivization through CEUs, user participation remained low. Additionally, the study was only active for three weeks due to time constraints from building the module. Having a longer participation window may have captured more participants. Furthermore, the study took place at only one institution with CRNAs. For generalizations to be drawn, data should be gathered from additional sites where CRNAs take the role of preceptors.

Future Recommendations

Although studies have shown no difference in the efficacy of an online format (Wu et al., 2022), some participants preferred an in-person education workshop. Directly comparing the effectiveness of an online preceptor education to an in-person version is an opportunity for future learning lessons. Likewise, a hybrid version of the CRNA preceptor education is another modality to explore. A hybrid model blends the flexibility and convenience of provider-directed online learning with the enhanced engagement of face-to-face discussion (Wu et al., 2018).

In addition to exploring a hybrid style of learning, ethnic and cultural diversity training is another opportunity for CRNA preceptor education. Despite having minimal significance, the data indicates a negative correlation between the years a CRNA has worked and their confidence in working with SRNAs from different ethnic backgrounds. This finding was also echoed in the pilot study by Butler et al., 2022, which highlights the need for additional research in this area. Exploring the deficiencies in ethnic and cultural education among CRNA preceptors is a prospective area for future research.

Lastly, future modifications to the preceptor education module should be made to increase ease of use and access. The addition of voice narration will cater to different learning styles and increase user accessibility. Inputting additional case-specific videos also offers content variability of the information to keep users engaged. Addressing minor technical issues, such as the timing of interactions and transitions between slides, may also enhance the user experience.

Conclusions

In conclusion, an online CRNA preceptor education module was modified from a pilot study to improve the CRNA precepting experience. The study measured the CRNA preceptor's comfort, confidence, satisfaction, and knowledge through pre- and post-module surveys. Due to the small data set, there were no significant changes in the preceptor's confidence, comfort,

satisfaction, or knowledge. As highlighted in the literature review, a gap exists in CRNA preceptor education, which was echoed in the findings from this study. Based on the encouraging feedback of the CRNAs at KPPCMC, the role of a CRNA preceptor educational module is promising. Furthermore, this DNP study demonstrates the feasibility of an online learning modality to deliver CRNA preceptor education. The project's authors hope that the findings and recommendations of this study will serve as a catalyst for future research in advancing the education of CRNAs as preceptors.

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Appendix A

The Iowa Model

Figure A1

The Iowa Model Revised

Note. Adapted from “Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation,” by Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017, *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 14(3), p. 178 (<https://doi.org/10.1111/wvn.12223>). Copyright 2015 by the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics. Reprinted with permission.

Figure A2

Iowa Model for Implementing an Online Preceptorship Training Module

Appendix B

International Review Board Approval

Figure B1

IRB Approval from Kaiser Permanente

InterOffice Memorandum

February 3, 2023

To: **Sandra Bordi, DNP, CRNA**
100 S. Los Robles Ave., Suite 501
Pasadena, CA 91188

Re: Implementing an Online Preceptorship Training Module for CRNAs

Dear Dr. Bordi,

A designated reviewer on the Kaiser Permanente Southern California (KPSC) Institutional Review Board (IRB) reviewed your submission and determined that this is not human subjects research as defined by 45 CFR 46.102 (e)(1) and (l). Therefore, IRB review of this project is not necessary.

Sincerely,

Armida Ayala, MHA, PhD
Director of Human Research Subjects Protection
Office/Institutional Review Board (IRB)

Figure B2

IRB Approval from California State University Fullerton

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON

Office of Research and Sponsored Projects

P.O. Box 6850 or 1121 N. State College Blvd., 2nd Fl., Fullerton, CA 92831 / T 657-278-7719 / F 657-278-7238

APPROVAL NOTICE

*From the Institutional Review Board
California State University, Fullerton*

April 12, 2023

**From: Dr. Matt Englar-Carlson, Chair
CSUF Institutional Review Board**

To: PI: Rachel McClanahan

Application No. HSR-22-23-271

Study Title: KPSA: Implementing an Online Preceptorship Training Module for CRNAs

Re: Initial Exempt Review

The forms you submitted to this office regarding the use of human participants in the above-referenced proposal have been reviewed by the Regulatory Compliance Coordinator and the Chair of the California State University, Fullerton, Institutional Review Board. Your proposal is determined to be Category 2.(ii). Research that only includes interactions involving educational tests (cognitive, diagnostic, aptitude, achievement), survey procedures, interview procedures, or observation of public behavior (including visual or auditory recording). Any disclosure of the human subjects' responses outside the research would not reasonably place the subjects at risk of criminal or civil liability or be damaging to the subjects' financial standing, employability, educational advancement, or reputation.

Appendix C

Surveys

Table C1

CRNA Preceptor Demographics Survey

Please answer the following questions:						
1. What is your gender?						
Male	Female		Non-binary / third gender		Prefer not to say	
2. Enter your age.						
3. Are you of Hispanic origin (e.g., Mexican, Latin American, Puerto Rican, Cuban)?						
I am Hispanic/Latino			I am not Hispanic/Latino			
4. Which of the following best describes you?						
American Indian or Alaska Native	Asian	Black or African American	Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander	White or Caucasian	Other	Race/Ethnicity Unknown
5. How many years have you worked as a nurse?						
< 5	6 - 10	11 - 15	16 - 20	20 - 25	> 25	
6. Were you an SRNA at Kaiser Permanente Panorama City Medical Center?						
Yes				No		
7. Nursing background (select all that apply):						
MICU	SICU	CCU	PICU	NICU	CVICU	ER PACU Other
8. Was your nurse anesthesia program front loaded? (i.e., most didactic coursework was completed before clinical rotations began)						
Yes				No		
9. Enter the amount of years you have been a CRNA.						
10. Enter the number of years you have worked at Kaiser Permanente Panorama City Medical Center.						
11. Highest degree completed (select one):						
Associates		Bachelors		Master's		Doctorate
12. Are you pursuing another degree at this time? If so, what degree level?						
Associates		Bachelors		Master's	Doctorate	Not Applicable
13. Have you ever attended a course for CRNA preceptor education?						
Yes				No		
14. Have you ever participated in preceptor education?						
Yes				No		
15. How many years have you been a SRNA preceptor at this facility?						
< 2	2 - 5		6 - 10		> 10	

Note. CCU: Cardiac care unit; CVICU: cardiovascular intensive care unit; CRNA: Certified

Registered Nurse Anesthetist; ER: emergency room; MICU: medical intensive care unit; NICU:

neonatal intensive care unit; PACU: postanesthesia care unit; PICU: pediatric intensive care unit; SICU: surgical intensive care unit; SRNA: student registered nurse anesthetist. Adapted from “A CRNA preceptor workshop to increase preceptor satisfaction, confidence, and comfort: A quality improvement project” by M. Scott-Herring and S. Singh, 2017b, *American Association of Nurse Anesthesia Journal*, 85(4), 26. Copyright 2017 by the American Association of Nurse Anesthesiology. Reprinted with permission.

Table C2*CRNA Preceptor Pre-module Survey*

Please rate:	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Neither Agree or Disagree</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
1. I am satisfied with my previous preparation regarding the education of SRNAs.	1	2	3	4	5
2. I am confident with my ability to precept a SRNA.	1	2	3	4	5
3. I am comfortable with actively coaching critical thinking with my SRNA.	1	2	3	4	5
4. I am comfortable working with a SRNA who may have a different personality or learning style than mine	1	2	3	4	5
5. I am confident with working with a SRNA of a different ethnic background than mine?	1	2	3	4	5
6. I am confident in providing positive feedback to a SRNA.	1	2	3	4	5
7. I am confident in providing constructive feedback to a SRNA.	1	2	3	4	5

Note. CRNA: certified registered nurse anesthetist; SRNA, student registered nurse anesthetist.

Adapted from “A CRNA preceptor workshop to increase preceptor satisfaction, confidence, and comfort: A quality improvement project” by M. Scott-Herring and S. Singh, 2017, *American Association of Nurse Anesthesia Journal*, 85(4), 27. Copyright 2017 by the American Association of Nurse Anesthesiology. Reprinted with permission.

Table C3*CRNA Preceptor Post-module Survey*

Please rate:	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Neither Agree or Disagree</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
1. I am satisfied with today's preparation regarding education of a SRNA.	1	2	3	4	5
2. I am confident with my ability to precept a SRNA.	1	2	3	4	5
3. I am comfortable in actively coaching critical thinking with my SRNA.	1	2	3	4	5
4. I am comfortable working with a SRNA who may have a different personality or learning style than mine	1	2	3	4	5
5. I am confident in working with a SRNA of a different ethnic background than mine.	1	2	3	4	5
6. I am confident in providing positive feedback to a SRNA.	1	2	3	4	5
7. I am confident in providing constructive feedback to a SRNA.	1	2	3	4	5
8. The educational module was easy to navigate.	1	2	3	4	5
9. The content of the module was easy to navigate.	1	2	3	4	5
10. What recommendations do you have to improve the module?					
11. If any technical issues occurred, please list them here.					

Note. CRNA: certified registered nurse anesthetist; SRNA, student registered nurse anesthetist.

Adapted from "A CRNA preceptor workshop to increase preceptor satisfaction, confidence, and comfort: A quality improvement project" by M. Scott-Herring and S. Singh, 2017b, *American Association of Nurse Anesthesia Journal*, 85(4), 27. Copyright 2017 by the American Association of Nurse Anesthesiology. Reprinted with permission.

Appendix D

Results

Table D1

CRNA Preceptor Demographics Survey Results

Demographics	Frequency (<i>n</i> = 9)	%
Gender		
Male	2	22.2%
Female	7	77.8%
Non-binary / third gender	0	0%
Prefer not to say	0	0%
Age		
30 years or less	1	11.1%
31 – 40 years	2	22.2%
41 – 50 years	3	33.3%
51 – 60 years	1	11.1%
More than 60 years	2	22.2%
Hispanic Origin		
Yes	2	22.2%
No	7	77.8%
Race/Ethnicity		
American Indian or Alaska Native	0	0%
Asian	2	22.2%
Black or African American	0	0%
Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander	0	0%
White or Caucasian	6	66.7%
Other	1	11.1%
Years of Nursing Experience		
5 years or less	1	11.1%
6 – 10 years	1	11.1%
11 – 15 years	1	11.1%
16 – 20 years	0	0%
20 – 25 years	2	22.2%
More than 25 years	4	44.4%
SRNA at KPPCMC		
Yes	3	33.3%
No	6	66.7%
Front-loaded Nurse Anesthesia Program		
Yes	4	44.4%
No	5	55.6%

Demographics	Frequency (<i>n</i> = 9)	Percentage
Years of CRNA Experience		
Less than 2 years	2	22.2%
2-5 years	0	0%
6-10 years	2	22.2%
11-15 years	1	11.1%
16-20 years	2	22.2%
21 or more	2	22.2%
Years at KPPCMC		
Less than 2 years	3	33.3%
2-5 years	1	11.1%
6-10 years	2	22.2%
11-15 years	1	11.1%
16-20 years	1	11.1%
21 or more	1	11.1%
Highest Degree Completed		
Associates	0	0%
Bachelors	0	0%
Masters	7	77.8%
Doctorate	2	22.2%
Pursuing Another Degree		
Associate's	0	0%
Bachelor's	0	0%
Master's	0	0%
Doctorate	2	22.2%
Not applicable	7	77.8%
Previous CRNA Preceptor Education		
Yes	2	22.2%
No	7	77.8%
Previous Nursing Preceptor Education		
Yes	5	44.4%
No	4	55.6%
Years as SRNA Preceptor at KPPCMC		
Less than 2 years	3	33.3%
2 – 5 years	2	22.2%
6 – 10 years	1	11.1%
More than 10 years	3	33.3%

Note. CRNA: certified registered nurse anesthetist; KPPCMC: Kaiser Permanente Panorama

City Medical Center; SRNA: student registered nurse anesthetist.

Table D2*Related-Samples Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test Results*

Statement	Z-value	p-value
I am satisfied with my preparation regarding education of a SRNA.	-1.66	.098
I am confident with my ability to precept a SRNA.	-.45	.655
I am comfortable with actively coaching critical thinking with my SRNA.	.00	1.000
I am comfortable working with a SRNA who may have a different personality or learning style than mine.	.00	1.000
I am confident with working with a SRNA of a different ethnic background than mine.	-1.00	.317
I am confident in providing positive feedback to a SRNA.	-1.00	.317
I am confident in providing constructive feedback to a SRNA.	.00	1.000

Note. SRNA = student registered nurse anesthetist.

Table D3

Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation Results

Statement		Amount of years worked at KPPCMC	Participant age
Pre-module statement 5: I am confident with working with a SRNA of a different ethnic background than mine.	Correlation Coefficient	-.55	
	<i>p</i> -value (2-tailed)	.125	
	<i>n</i>	9	
Post-module statement 5: I am confident with working with a SRNA of a different ethnic background than mine.	Correlation Coefficient	-.52	
	<i>p</i> -value (2-tailed)	.152	
	<i>n</i>	9	
Post-module statement 8: The educational module was easy to navigate.	Correlation Coefficient		.06
	<i>p</i> -value (2-tailed)		.889
	<i>n</i>		9
Post-module statement 9: The content of the module was easy to navigate.	Correlation Coefficient		.08
	<i>p</i> -value (2-tailed)		.849
	<i>n</i>		9

Note. KPPCMC = Kaiser Permanente Panorama City Medical Center; SRNA = student registered nurse anesthetist.

Table D4*Post-Survey Open Ended Questions and Responses*

Participant #	What recommendations do you have to improve the module	If any technical issues occurred, please list them here.
HPT 004	Employ more the Cognitive theory of multimedia learning; specifically the principle which states that people learn better when they can advance the presentation at their own pace. I feel the first drag and match definition slide was questionable.	Sometimes a slide would be repeated when next was selected
HPT 007	In person learning I feel would help this educational piece	Took a while to advance some slides when clicking on next
HPT 009	Videos were easy and fun to watch, would suggest reframing some questions: ie: I am comfortable with actively coaching critical thinking with MY SRNA...netter to state THE SRNA	none
HPT 013	Make it a requirement for CRNAs to take training modules in order to precept.	Make it a requirement for clinical coordinators to take educational modules on precepting.
HPT 016	too long :)	none
HPT 017	Have the ability to adjust playback speed of module	none
HPT 021	n/a	none
HPT 023	none	none
HPT 032	Add audio to each slide with activity	none

Appendix E
Project Timeline

Planned dates:	Tasks:
January – February 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applied to Kaiser IRB • Applied to Cayuse • Modify preceptorship module based on pilot data
March - April 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapt preceptorship module from Articulate Rise to Storyline • Continued to modify preceptorship module • Applied for AANA CEUs for module
May 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developed preceptorship module presentation
June – July 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continued to modify preceptorship • AANA CEUs approved
August 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Met with instructional design librarian • Finalized changes to online module
September 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uploaded module on Moodle website • Met with KPSA informational technology engineer
October 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Met and introduced module presentation to anesthesia faculty in Kaiser Permanente Panorama City Medical Center • Deployed preceptorship module • Reminders sent to CRNAs • Deadline for CRNAs to finish preceptorship module
November 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Began write-up of full doctoral project paper and defense presentation • Made revisions to paper and presentation based upon TL/TM feedback • Developed project poster
December 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finalized project paper and presentation • Finalized project poster